

UTILIZATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TOOLS IN ADDRESSING THE CHALLENGES OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

The study determined the utilization of artificial intelligence tools in addressing the challenges of Sustainable Development Goals in public universities in Enugu State, Nigeria. It was guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population comprised 4864 (2,944 males and 1920 females) academic staff in the three public universities in Enugu State. The sample size was 486 respondents which comprised (296 males and 190 females) academic staff. The sample size was determined using stratified proportionate random sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher titled “Utilization of Artificial Intelligence tools in addressing the challenges of Sustainable Development Goals Questionnaire (UAIACSDGQ)”. The instrument was subjected to validation by three specialists from Enugu State University of Science and Technology, two in Educational Management and one in Measurement and Evaluation. Reliability testing produced coefficients of 0.81 for cluster one and 0.80 for cluster two, with an overall reliability index of 0.82, confirming its consistency. Research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation, while the null hypotheses were tested with t-test statistics. The data indicates that the use of Google TensorFlow in addressing SDGs in Enugu State public universities remains low, with consistent perceptions across gender. The findings demonstrate that IBM Watson is generally underutilized in addressing Sustainable Development Goals in public universities in Enugu State. In line with the findings, it is recommended that university management organize regular training and workshops to build staff capacity in the effective use of AI tools such as Google TensorFlow and IBM Watson. Institutions should also invest in the necessary digital infrastructure to support the seamless integration of these technologies into teaching, research, and community development projects.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Artificial Intelligence Tools, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Public Universities, Utilization

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to the development of computer systems capable of performing tasks that typically require human

intelligence, such as problem-solving, learning, and decision-making. Artificial Intelligence is defined as the study of agents that receive percepts from the environment and perform

actions that maximize their chances of achieving goals (Russell & Norvig, 2016). According to Kaplan and Haenlein (2019), artificial Intelligence is a system's ability to correctly interpret external data, learn from such data, and use that learning to achieve specific goals and tasks through flexible adaptation.

In education, AI is increasingly used to personalize learning, provide intelligent tutoring, and support administrative efficiency, thereby improving teaching and learning outcomes. In research, AI tools such as machine learning algorithms and natural language processing assist in data analysis, pattern recognition, and predictive modeling, which enhance the quality and speed of scholarly investigations. Furthermore, in development sectors, AI contributes to solving global challenges by supporting innovations in healthcare, agriculture, and environmental sustainability. According to Okonkwo and Ade-Ibijola (2021), as well as Oke and Fernandes (2020), AI has become a critical driver of innovation and a catalyst for achieving sustainable development in Africa and beyond. Artificial Intelligence has emerged as a transformative tool in solving complex problems and supporting evidence-based decision-making. Artificial Intelligence tools are technologies designed to simulate human intelligence for problem-solving, learning, and decision-making, and they include Google TensorFlow, IBM Watson, Microsoft Azure AI, Amazon SageMaker, and OpenAI GPT. However, the present study focused on Google TensorFlow and IBM Watson.

Google TensorFlow is an open-source artificial intelligence framework developed by Google for building and deploying machine learning and deep learning models. It provides a flexible ecosystem of tools, libraries, and community resources that

enable researchers and developers to train and deploy AI systems across platforms, from cloud services to mobile devices. TensorFlow has been widely adopted in education, healthcare, and scientific research for tasks such as image recognition, natural language processing, and predictive analytics (Abadi et al., 2016). Both Google TensorFlow and IBM Watson are transformative Artificial Intelligence tools that complement each other in advancing education, research, and sustainable development, with the greater focus on IBM Watson.

IBM Watson is a suite of artificial intelligence services and applications developed by IBM, designed to analyze large volumes of unstructured data and provide insights through natural language processing and machine learning. IBM Watson helps organizations make data-driven decisions, automate processes, and improve efficiency in addressing complex challenges (Ferrucci, 2012). Both Google TensorFlow and IBM Watson are powerful Artificial Intelligence tools that resolve data-driven solutions in education, research, healthcare, and sustainable development. Here, TensorFlow serves as an open-source platform for model building and Watson excelling in natural language processing and cognitive computing, culminating in IBM Watson. Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools such as Google TensorFlow and IBM Watson are increasingly being applied to advance the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) across the world.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a set of 17 interconnected global objectives adopted by the United Nations in 2015 to guide international efforts toward ending poverty, protecting the planet, and ensuring prosperity for all by 2030. They provide a universal framework that addresses critical issues such as quality education, gender equality, climate action, and

reduced inequalities. The SDGs are particularly important because they emphasize inclusiveness, requiring governments, institutions, and individuals to collaborate in achieving sustainable development across all sectors. In the context of higher education, universities are seen as key players in driving SDGs through research, innovation, and human capacity development. According to Sachs et al. (2019), the SDGs offer a roadmap for integrating economic growth with social inclusion and environmental sustainability. Similarly, United Nations (2015) and Mortensen and Bloch (2021) argue that, the SDGs remain central to global development discourse and provide benchmarks for measuring progress across nations. In line with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), AI has been applied to improve healthcare delivery, agricultural productivity, environmental sustainability, and educational systems across the globe.

In education, AI supports personalized learning and intelligent tutoring, thereby enhancing student outcomes and teaching efficiency (Holmes et al., 2021). In healthcare, AI applications aid in disease diagnosis, drug discovery, and predictive health management, thereby, contributing to SDG 3 on good health and well-being (Topol, 2019). Environmental sustainability also benefits from AI, as tools are deployed to monitor climate change, optimize energy systems, and improve resource management, thus, aligning with SDG 13 on climate action (Rolnick et al., 2019). In addressing poverty and hunger, AI innovations such as precision agriculture and crop monitoring improve food security and rural livelihoods, supporting SDG 1 and SDG 2 (Shamim et al., 2021). Furthermore, AI-powered analytics enhance institutional governance by improving transparency, data-driven decision-making, and

service delivery, which advance SDG 16 on peace, justice, and strong institutions (Vinuesa et al., 2020).

In Nigeria, the adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to support the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) remains limited due to systemic challenges in higher education. The SDGs are a global framework established by the United Nations in 2015 to guide global efforts on poverty, inequality, quality education, and climate action by 2030 especially Goal 4 on Quality Education, which ensures inclusive, equitable learning and equips learners with skills needed for sustainable development (United Nations, 2015). Integrating AI into higher education could transform research, enhance teaching through personalized learning and intelligent assessment, expand inclusive access, and streamline institutional management. Yet, in Nigeria, this potential largely goes unrealized: weak digital infrastructure, insufficient funding, low AI literacy among faculty coupled with scarce training, and poor policy frameworks create formidable barriers (Okoye & Ogu, 2023; Ibrahim, Adepoju & Salami, 2024). These systemic deficits hinder AI's capacity to serve as a powerful educational tool in advancing the SDGs through Nigerian universities.

Public universities in Enugu State, which should serve as hubs for research and innovation, struggle with poor access to advanced technologies and inadequate digital infrastructure (Ukeh & Anih, 2024). Chronic underfunding of the education sector further constrains the ability of these institutions to invest in AI laboratories, software, and skilled personnel. Limited awareness and insufficient training among academic staff also hinder the effective integration of AI tools into teaching, research, and institutional governance. These challenges slow down progress toward

achieving key SDGs such as quality education (SDG 4), industry and innovation (SDG 9), and strong institutions (SDG 16). As a result, universities in Enugu State risk lagging behind in leveraging AI to address pressing developmental needs compared to their global counterparts.

Despite the growing global relevance of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in promoting sustainable development, its utilization in Nigerian public universities remains limited. In Enugu State, universities face persistent challenges in achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), yet AI tools such as Google TensorFlow and IBM Watson are scarcely applied to address these issues. Factors such as inadequate infrastructure, low awareness, and insufficient staff training hinder the effective integration of AI into teaching, research, and community development. This underutilization raises concerns about the capacity of public universities in Enugu State to leverage AI for advancing SDG-related initiatives and achieving meaningful impact. The general purpose of the study determined the utilization of artificial intelligence tools in addressing the challenges of sustainable development goals in public universities in Enugu State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to ascertain the extent to which:

Objective 1: Google TensorFlow is utilized in addressing the challenges of sustainable development goals in public universities in Enugu State, Nigeria;

Objective 2: IBM Watson is utilized in addressing the challenges of sustainable development goals in public universities in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Research Question 1: To what extent is Google TensorFlow utilized in addressing the challenges of sustainable development goals in public universities in Enugu State, Nigeria?

Research Question 2: To what extent is IBM Watson utilized in addressing the challenges of sustainable development goals in public universities in Enugu State, Nigeria?

Hypothesis HO₁: No significant difference exists in the mean ratings of male and female academic staff on the extent to which Google TensorFlow is utilized in addressing the challenges of sustainable development goals in public universities in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis HO₂: No significant difference exists in the mean ratings of male and female academic staff on the extent to which IBM Watson is utilized in addressing the challenges of sustainable development goals in public universities in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

A literature review tells the story of what other researchers have discovered about a topic, pointing out the main ideas, results, and the spaces that still need to be explored. It lays the groundwork for a new study by showing how it fits into, challenges, or extends what has already been done.

Concept of Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the simulation of human intelligence in machines designed to think, learn, and act in ways similar to humans. It is a field of study and engineering concerned with developing systems that display intelligent behavior, such as reasoning and problem-solving (Sanoff, 2022). AI equips machines with human-like capabilities, enabling them to process information, make decisions, and solve problems across different contexts. For researchers, AI has become an essential tool for the efficient collection, organization, and analysis of large datasets, including statistical evaluations of vast research outputs (Al-Ameri & Hameed, 2023). Ukeh and Anih (2024) posited that, AI also holds

great promise in transforming the teaching and learning process in higher education. It supports personalized learning, intelligent tutoring, collaboration, and automation of routine tasks such as grading (Chander, 2021). Through adaptive and computationally efficient models, AI helps tailor courses to match learners' competencies, thereby, ensuring a more effective pace of study. The adoption of AI in universities has led to more flexible and effective educational models (Iryna, 2023). It encompasses technologies that perform tasks requiring human intelligence, such as language processing, decision-making, visual perception, and speech recognition. With increasing interest in education, AI is now applied through intelligent books, browsers, apps, and digital learning platforms (Karsenti, 2019). These innovations have introduced new approaches to learning, teaching, and assessment, making education more efficient, accessible, and information-rich.

Artificial Intelligence, with its ability to simulate human intelligence and process large volumes of data, provides powerful tools such as Google TensorFlow and IBM Watson that can be applied to solving complex developmental challenges. In the context of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), these tools can support universities in Enugu State by enabling advanced research, data-driven decision-making, and innovative problem-solving approaches. Their application in higher education can enhance teaching, learning, and research efficiency, thereby aligning academic activities with global sustainability objectives. However, the extent to which these AI tools are utilized in Enugu State public universities determines the capacity of the institutions to contribute meaningfully to achieving the SDGs.

Overview of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were introduced by the United Nations in 2015 as a universal framework for addressing global challenges. They consist of 17 goals and 169 targets designed to promote peace, prosperity, and environmental sustainability by the year 2030. The SDGs build on the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), expanding their scope to include pressing issues such as climate action, innovation, reduced inequalities, and responsible consumption. Unlike the MDGs, which focused mainly on developing countries, the SDGs are universal, applying to all nations regardless of income level. Each goal addresses a specific dimension of sustainable development, including poverty eradication, quality education, gender equality, clean energy, and decent work. The vision of the SDGs is to ensure a balance between economic growth, social inclusion, and environmental protection. Achieving these goals requires collaboration among governments, civil society, private sectors, and academic institutions. Universities play a vital role by conducting research, fostering innovation, and equipping students with the knowledge and skills to advance sustainable solutions. Despite their importance, progress toward achieving the SDGs has been uneven across regions, with developing countries facing significant challenges such as limited funding, weak institutions, and inadequate infrastructure. In Nigeria, for instance, issues like poverty, poor healthcare, gender disparities, and inadequate access to quality education remain critical barriers. Public universities, particularly in Enugu State, have a unique opportunity to use research and technology, including Artificial Intelligence (AI), to contribute to addressing these challenges. The SDGs therefore serve not only as a global roadmap for development but also as a

call to action for academic institutions to drive evidence-based solutions.

Theoretical Framework

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was propounded by Fred Davis in 1989 as an extension of Ajzen and Fishbein's Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA). TAM was developed to explain how users come to accept and use technology. The model is based on two key constructs: perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU). Perceived usefulness refers to the extent to which an individual believes that, using a technology will enhance their job performance. Perceived ease of use, on the other hand, describes the degree to which a person believes that using the technology will be free from effort. According to Davis, these two factors directly influence an individual's attitude toward using technology, which then affects their behavioural intention to use it. Over time, TAM has been widely adopted in studies of information systems, e-learning, artificial intelligence, and digital tools in higher education. The model is relevant in examining the utilization of AI tools such as Google TensorFlow and IBM Watson in addressing Sustainable Development Goals in universities. Its strength lies in providing a clear framework to understand why individuals accept or reject new technologies. However, scholars have also extended TAM to include external variables such as social influence, institutional support, and facilitating conditions to better capture real-world technology adoption.

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is significant to this study because it explains how perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use influence academic staff's willingness to adopt AI tools such as Google TensorFlow and IBM Watson. It provides a framework for understanding the factors that drive or hinder the

utilization of these technologies in addressing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) within public universities in Enugu State. By applying TAM, the study can identify key areas such as awareness, training, and institutional support that must be strengthened to enhance AI adoption for sustainable development.

Methodology

A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. According to Nworgu (2018), a descriptive survey research design involves studying a population by gathering and analyzing data from a selected sample of individuals or items, which are considered to represent the entire group. The population comprised 4864 (2,944 male and 1920 female) academic staff in the three public universities in Enugu State. The sample size was 486 respondents which comprised (296 male and 190 female) academic staff. The sample size was determined using stratified proportionate random sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher titled "Utilization of Artificial Intelligence tools in addressing the challenges of Sustainable Development Goals Questionnaire (UAIACSDGQ)". The instrument was subjected to validation by three specialists from Enugu State University of Science and Technology, two in Educational Management and one in Measurement and Evaluation. Reliability testing produced coefficients of 0.81 for cluster one and 0.80 for cluster two, with an overall reliability index of 0.82, confirming its consistency. However, out of the 486 copies of questionnaire administered, the researcher retrieved 477 copies (286 from male and 191 from female) academic staff which resulted to 98.15% return rate. The research questions were answered using mean scores and standard deviation. The extent of responses was determined by calculating the mean of the values

assigned to each option. The decision rule was guided by the real limits of numbers: Very Great Extent (VGE) = 3.50–4.00; Great Extent (GE) = 2.50–3.49; Low Extent (LE) = 1.50–2.49; and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 0.00–1.49. The hypotheses were tested using a t-test at the 0.05 level of significance, where a p-value greater than

0.05 led to retention of the hypothesis, while a p-value less than 0.05 resulted in its rejection.

Results Presentation

Research Question 1: To what extent is Google TensorFlow utilized in addressing the challenges of Sustainable Development Goals in public universities in Enugu State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviation of male and female academic staff on the extent to which Google TensorFlow is utilized in addressing the challenges of Sustainable Development Goals in public universities

ITEMS		Male Academic Staff 286	Female Academic Staff 191	Overall 477				
S/N	Google TensorFlow is utilized in addressing the challenges of Sustainable Development Goals in public universities when:	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	Dec
1	Predictive Analytics for Student Dropout Prevention	1.57	.80	1.56	.81	1.57	.81	LE
2	AI-Powered Agricultural Solutions	1.59	.83	1.50	.81	1.55	.82	LE
3	Renewable Energy Optimization	1.51	.85	1.53	.83	1.52	.84	LE
4	Climate Change Modelling	1.58	.82	1.56	.82	1.57	.82	LE
5	Healthcare Diagnostics	1.56	.84	1.58	.84	1.57	.84	LE
6	Natural Language Processing for Education	1.69	.82	1.71	.80	1.70	.81	LE
Cluster Mean/SD		1.58	.83	1.57	.82	1.58	.82	LE

The findings in Table 1 reveal that male academic staff reported a cluster mean of 1.58 (SD = .83) while female academic staff reported 1.57 (SD = .82) on the extent of utilization of Google TensorFlow for addressing SDGs. The overall cluster mean of 1.58 with a standard deviation of .82 shows that, Google TensorFlow is utilized to a low extent (LE) in public universities. Across the items, Natural Language Processing for Education recorded the highest overall mean (1.70, SD = .81), whereas Renewable Energy Optimization had the lowest (1.52, SD = .84). The standard

deviation values (ranging from .80 to .85) are close, indicating minimal variation in responses and suggesting that both male and female academic staff hold similar views. The data indicates that the use of Google TensorFlow in addressing SDGs in Enugu State public universities remains low, with consistent perceptions across gender.

Research Question 2: To what extent is IBM Watson utilized in addressing the challenges of Sustainable Development Goals in public universities in Enugu State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean scores and standard deviation of male and female academic staff on the extent to which IBM Watson is utilized in addressing the challenges of Sustainable Development Goals in public universities

ITEMS		Male Academic Staff 286	Female Academic Staff 191	Overall 477				
S/N	IBM Watson is utilized in addressing the challenges of Sustainable Development Goals in public universities when:	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	Dec
7	AI-Powered virtual academic advisors.	1.58	.80	1.56	.81	1.57	.81	LE
8	Smart campus energy management	1.59	.83	1.50	.81	1.55	.82	LE
9	Campus security.	1.55	.85	1.54	.83	1.55	.84	LE
10	Career guidance systems.	1.50	.82	1.56	.82	1.53	.82	LE
11	Safety monitoring.	1.58	.84	1.56	.84	1.57	.84	LE
12	Forecasting.	1.60	.82	1.58	.80	1.59	.81	LE
Cluster Mean/SD		1.56	.83	1.55	.82	1.56	.82	LE

The results in Table 2 show that male academic staff had a cluster mean of 1.56 (SD = .83), while female academic staff recorded 1.55 (SD = .82) on the extent of IBM Watson utilization for addressing SDGs. The overall cluster mean of 1.56 with a standard deviation of .82 indicates that IBM Watson is utilized to a low extent (LE) in public universities. Among the listed items, Forecasting had the highest overall mean (1.59, SD = .81), while Career Guidance Systems had the lowest (1.53, SD = .82). The standard deviation values, which range narrowly between

.80 and .85, suggest low variability and show that male and female staff opinions were largely consistent. The findings demonstrate that IBM Watson is generally underutilized in addressing Sustainable Development Goals in public universities in Enugu State.

Hypothesis HO₁: No significant difference exists in the mean ratings of male and female academic staff on the extent to which Google TensorFlow is utilized in addressing the challenges of Sustainable Development Goals in public universities in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean scores of male and female academic staff on the extent to which Google TensorFlow is utilized in addressing the challenges of Sustainable Development Goals in public universities

Group	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	p-value	Decision
Male Academic Staff	286	1.58	.83	475	.085	H ₀₁ not rejected
Female Academic Staff	191	1.57	.82			

The t-test result in Table 3 shows that male academic staff had a mean score of 1.58 (SD = .83) while female academic staff had 1.57 (SD = .82). With $df = 475$ and a p-value of .085, which is greater than 0.05, the difference between the two groups is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) was not rejected, indicating no significant difference in their responses. This implies that, both male and female

academic staff share similar views on the extent to which Google TensorFlow is utilized in addressing SDGs in public universities.

Hypothesis H_{02} : No significant difference exists in the mean ratings of male and female academic staff on the extent to which IBM Watson is utilized in addressing the challenges of Sustainable Development Goals in public universities in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean scores of male and female academic staff on the extent to which IBM Watson is utilized in addressing the challenges of Sustainable Development Goals in public universities

Group	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	p-value	Decision
Male Academic Staff	286	1.56	.83	475	.061	H_{02} not rejected
Female Academic Staff	191	1.55	.82			

The t-test result in Table 4 shows that male academic staff had a mean score of 1.56 (SD = .83) while female academic staff recorded 1.55 (SD = .82). With $df = 475$ and a p-value of .061, which is greater than 0.05, the difference between the two groups is not statistically significant. As a result, the null hypothesis (H_{02}) was not rejected, indicating no significant difference in their responses. This suggests that both male and female academic staff hold similar perceptions regarding the extent to which IBM Watson is utilized in addressing SDGs in public universities.

Discussion

The data shows that, Google TensorFlow is not widely applied in tackling Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) within public universities in Enugu State. Both male and female academic staff share similar views, suggesting that gender does not significantly influence its level of

adoption. This highlights a general underutilization of the tool, pointing to the need for increased awareness and training among staff to maximize its potential for addressing SDG-related challenges. The findings agree with Ajayi (2024), who observed that, although awareness of AI tools like TensorFlow is relatively high among Library and Information Science educators in Nigeria, their actual utilization remains very low due to infrastructural challenges and resistance to change. They also align with Abubakar et al. (2024), who reported that students in North-Central Nigerian institutions showed only moderate awareness of AI, with adoption constrained by lack of training and technical support. Together, these studies emphasize that the underutilization of TensorFlow in addressing SDGs in Enugu State universities reflects a

broader national trend that calls for targeted awareness and capacity-building programmes.

The findings reveal that IBM Watson is scarcely utilized in addressing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in public universities across Enugu State. Male and female academic staff reported similar views, showing no significant gender-based differences in its adoption. This uniform perception underscores the overall low integration of IBM Watson and the need for institutional support to enhance its effective use in achieving SDG-related objectives. The findings agree with Okiki (2022), who noted that, while artificial intelligence tools such as IBM Watson hold great potential for higher education in Nigeria, their adoption remains low due to inadequate institutional support and poor digital infrastructure. They also align with Abubakar et al. (2024), who found that students in North-Central Nigerian institutions had only moderate awareness of AI tools, with effective utilization limited by insufficient training and technical expertise. These studies reinforce the evidence that the scarce use of IBM Watson in addressing SDGs in Enugu State universities reflects broader systemic challenges that require stronger institutional investment and staff development initiatives.

Conclusion

This study established that, both Google TensorFlow and IBM Watson are scarcely utilized in addressing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in public universities across Enugu State. The results further revealed that perceptions of underutilization were consistent across gender, indicating that the challenge is systemic rather than gender-based. This low level of adoption suggests that these advanced AI tools have not yet been fully integrated into academic and research practices within the universities. The situation

highlights the urgent need for awareness creation, capacity building, and institutional support to strengthen the use of AI tools in advancing SDG-related initiatives. Therefore, universities and policymakers must prioritize training, infrastructure development, and policy frameworks to enhance the effective deployment of AI technologies for sustainable development.

In line with the findings, it is recommended that university management organize regular training and workshops to build staff capacity in the effective use of AI tools such as Google TensorFlow and IBM Watson. Institutions should also invest in the necessary digital infrastructure to support the seamless integration of these technologies into teaching, research, and community development projects. Policymakers and government agencies should provide funding and supportive policies that encourage the adoption of AI for achieving SDGs in higher education. Furthermore, collaborations with technology companies should be strengthened to provide technical support and continuous professional development for academic staff.

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